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Prenatal assessment of ventriculomegaly: an anatomical study

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Summary

Background:

The aim of the study was to analyze the development of the lateral ventricles during the 1st and 2nd trimester of fetal life using computerized image processing, and to compare the findings with the results obtained by ultrasound imaging and MRI.

Material/Methods:

The material consisted of 32 fetuses from spontaneous abortions, 54–235 mm crown-rump length. After detached craniotomy, the brains were cut into axial sections; the sections were filmed with a video camera and then analyzed using specialized software packages.

Results:

In 12 analyzed brains, no significant pathological changes were observed in the cerebral hemispheres, whereas the remaining 20 (63%) demonstrated visible pathology. In 10 cases there were areas of leukomalacia, in 5 intra- and periventricular hemorrhages, and in 2 fetuses ventriculomegaly with lateral ventricular triangles over 10 mm wide (in cases of active hydrocephalus and colpocephaly). In 1 case of an 18-week-old fetus, lateral ventricular morphology typical of hydrocephalus (generalized distension) was observed with ventricular triangles 8.5 mm wide. The other 2 fetuses demonstrated developmental defects. The frontal horns were the most markedly enlarged in both cases of hydrocephalus (100%) and were semicircular, whereas after intra- and periventricular hemorrhages they were less enlarged and triangular, with the base of the triangle directed to the front and frequent significant asymmetry.

Conclusions:

The shape of the ventricular system, including that of the frontal horns, is important in the diagnostics of fetal CNS.

key words:

fetal lateral ventricles • ventriculomegaly

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BACKGROUND

The nervous system as it develops during the fetal period is the organ most sensible to damage [1]. Many CNS defects can be diagnosed prenatally [2]. Assessment of the cerebral ventricles is an indispensable part of ultrasonography (USG) of the fetus [3]. Ventriculomegaly is commonly considered to be the 'tip of the iceberg' in cases of CNS anomalies [4]. Before the introduction of ultrasonography to clinical practice, interest in the fetal ventricular system was marginal, limited to anatomical studies. Only a few papers were published on the lateral ventricles of human fetuses. Westergaard filled the lateral ventricles of smaller fetuses with dye [5]. Ultrafast MRI techniques are now opening up new possibilities of *in vivo* assessment of the fetal CNS and more precise evaluation of the ventricles [6]. Levine et al. demonstrated that lateral ventricular shapes differ depending on the type of CNS anomalies [7]. In the embryonic cerebral vesicles, ventricles are formed that communicate with one another and with the lumen of the spinal cord [8,9]. The telencephalic vesicles grow in an arch-like pattern from the front towards the back, with the spiral bending outward, resembling the horns of a ram. This growth pattern is referred to as hemispheric rotation [10]. The frontal horns are formed first, then the temporal, and finally the occipital [11]. Soon after the formation of the ventricular system, the choroid plexus develops, first in the fourth ventricle, then in the lateral ventricles, and finally in the third ventricle [12]. The fetal ventricular system remains relatively wide up to the 4th month of fetal life. Then, the formation of Magendi and Luschka's foramina allows the outflow and circulation of the cerebro-spinal fluid (CSF) [13]. The size of the ventricular system and the choroid plexus does not undergo significant changes in the second and third trimester, whereas rapid growth of the telencephalon is observed during that period [14]. It has been established that, for reasons that remain unclear, the distal portion of the lateral ventricular system (atrium) or the proximal portion of the occipital horn remains unchanged throughout the second and third trimester of pregnancy. The dimensions of the atrium are identical between the 14th and 30th week of pregnancy, so it is unnecessary to know the age of the fetus or the tables of indexes to determine the normal dimensions of the atrium. This site has been accepted as the optimal location for the measurement of the lateral ventricles [15–18].

There are three mechanisms known to lead to enlargement of the ventricular system during the fetal period:

- abnormal development of the ventricles and surrounding cerebral tissue;
- obstructive hydrocephalus;
- destruction of the surrounding cerebral tissue [19].

Hydrocephalus is defined as enlargement of the lateral ventricular atria accompanied by a disproportional increase of head circumference [20]. In some cases, disproportional enlargement of the occipital horns in comparison with the frontal horns is observed. Such a configuration of the ventricular system was termed by

Yakovlev and Wadsworth as 'colpocephaly' [21]. Colpocephaly was later defined as persistent primary embryonic configuration present after the 6th month of fetal life. Thus, disproportional enlargement of the occipital horns is regarded as normal before the 6th month [22]. Ca. 15–20% of fetuses with ventriculomegaly demonstrate only slight distension of the ventricular system, which subsides spontaneously before birth, so that the neonate seems to be normal [23]. In some fetuses with the dimensions of the ventricular system exceeding 10 mm, no other anomalies can be detected despite detailed studies. The development of most of these fetuses is normal [24]. Isolated mild ventriculomegaly with the width of the atrium ranging from 10 to 15 mm is a serious diagnostic problem. Such a condition is believed to indicate disorders of the nervous system of various etiology [25–29].

Prenatal assessment of the cerebral ventricular system is of great clinical significance [30]. Ventriculomegaly, often very slight, is associated with many developmental anomalies of the CNS [31]. It is most frequently detected by USG at the beginning of the 3rd trimester of pregnancy (week 25±6) [30]. The aim of our study was to assess the ventricular system in the earlier period, from the late 1st trimester through the 2nd, to investigate the growth dynamics of the lateral ventricles and analyze normal and pathologic changes in their shape, and to search for correlations between the growth of the ventricular system and that of the cerebral hemispheres, the skull, and the increase of the crown-rump length of the fetus. Owing to computer-aided analysis of image and measurement tools, it is possible to obtain measurements of very high accuracy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was carried out on 37 fetuses from spontaneous abortions, ranging in size from 54 to 235 mm crown-rump. The external measurements of the fetuses (the crown-rump dimension, and the lateral and sagittal dimension of the cranium) were performed using a Mitotoyo electronic slide ruler. The circumferences of the head and chest were also measured. In order to obtain reproducible cross-section planes, the fetuses were mounted in a special apparatus for preparation and cutting. The external auditory meati served as the head fixing points. After detached craniotomy, the brains were cut in horizontal planes from the supraventricular to the basal layers, using a special guide allowing precise determination of layer thickness. The brain sections were recorded on video tape using a video camera mounted on a stand, and transferred to the memory of a computer equipped with a graphic card. Individual images were processed using ELF and Scion for Windows software packages. The largest width of the lateral ventricular bodies and triangles, as well as the occipital horns, was measured in the images, and the shape of the ventricular system was analyzed. The technique of computer-aided image analysis makes it possible to avoid direct manipulation of the preparations, and, consequently, artifacts caused by damage to delicate nervous tissue. After binarization of the axial section images, it is possible to measure the areas of the cerebral hemispheres and the ventricular system.

Table 1. Fetal ventricle measurements.

Lp.	Sex	C-R	HBD	Head width cm	Head length cm	Head circ, cm	Chest circ	Side	Ventricular		Corpus area mm
									Length mm	Width mm	
1.	M	20.0	21	5.30	7.95	22.0	17.5	L	26.86	4.11	71.4
								R	29.92	3.36	86.3
2.	M	6.68	11	1.98	2.42	7.0	7.0	L	16.50	8.01	109.4
								R	17.58	6.45	88.4
3.	M	6.08	11	2.14	3.16	8.5	7.5			Malacia	Malacia
4.	F	14.49	17	4.53	5.77	16.5	14.5			Malacia	Malacia
5.	M	15.19	18	4.40	5.15	15.5	13.0	L	22.92	2.79	30.15
								R	26.92	5.16	61.41
6.	F	19.0	20	5.57	6.33	20.2	18.5	L	28.53	4.59	68.97
								R	26.14	3.99	64.56
7.	F	20.0	21	5.60	7.23	20.5	18.0	L	22.82	2.39	20.05
								R	20.51	2.74	46.11
8.	M	18.0	19	5.61	7.41	20.7	19.0	L	32.22	8.46	211.9
								R	38.20	5.56	184.9
9.	M	13.20	16	3.19	4.83	14.2	13.0			Malacia	Malacia
10.	F	15.52	18	4.19	6.10	16.5	15.5	L	23.65	3.51	63.99
								R	21.10	3.01	25.40
11.	F	17.40	19	5.22	5.60	17.7	15.5	L	19.50	1.10	5.27
								R	21.10	1.09	5.40
12.	F	12.65	15	4.70	4.88	15.4	12.5	L	22.74	8.97	139.6
								R	26.02	7.27	171.4
13.	M	14.0	16	2.96	5.39	13.7	12.6		Deformation	Deformation	Deformation
14.	F	18.20	19	5.40	7.11	20.1	16.7	L	8.46	2.1	10.4
								R	2.78	1.0	2.0
15.	M	18.20	19	5.25	6.15	19.8	17.7	L	Invisible	2.1	Invisible
								R	Invisible	2.0	Invisible
16.	M	16.20	18	5.32	5.93	17.9	16.0	L	28.11	6.61	122.4
								R	29.06	8.06	162.6
17.	M	20.50	22	5.92	6.87	20.7	17.8	L	8.46	0.59	2.0
								R	16.28	2.28	16.89
18.	F	19.80	21	4.98	7.47	20.3	17.0	L	14.27	2.7	28.17
								R	11.27	3.0	29.06
19.	F	15.50	18	4.88	5.93	17.5	14.5	L	19.49	3.10	11.23
								R	11.69	1.69	1.20
20.	M	5.45	10	1.81	2.18	5.9	5.7	L	11.18	4.19	37.03
								R	11.58	3.78	43.60
21.	M	18.0	19	5.13	6.12	18.4	18.0	L	19.17	5.08	71.89
								R	21.44	5.08	79.92
22.	M	15.50	18	4.38	5.90	17.0	16.3	L		Malacia	Malacia
								R			
23.	F	23.50	24	5.11	8.00	22.0	19.0	L	Deformation	2.18	No
								R	21.69	2.32	No
24.	M	18.70	20	4.90	6.89	19.8	17.5	L	9.72	2.85	20.08
								R	10.34	3.37	22.15
25.	M	20.0	21	5.73	6.81	20.6	15.2	L	23.57	1.0	3.81
								R	26.64	2.77	9.71
26.	M	19.0	20	5.06	6.50	18.8	15.2	L	12.61	0.5	2.79
								R	16.76	2.21	6.47
27.	M	16.0	18			19.8			Encephalocel	Encephalocel	Encephalocel
28.	F	18.0	19	4.79	7.31	20.5	18.9	L	Invisible		
								R	Invisible		
29.	M	18.5	20	4.95	6.73	19.5	17.5	L	Invisible		
								R	Invisible		
30.	F	16.0	18	4.32	5.83	17.0	14.3	L	Invisible		
								R	Invisible		
31.	M	18.0	19	4.99	6.45	18.6	16.8	L	9.69	1.68	11.79
								R	9.52	1.71	13.21

Table 1. Continuous 1.

Lp.	Sex	C-R	HBD	Head width cm	Head length cm	Head circ, cm	Chest circ	Side	Ventricular		Corpus area mm
									Length mm	Width mm	
32.	M	19.3	20	5.50	6.90	19.5	17.5	L	5.67	1.80	10.86
								R	5.39	2.09	7.78
33.	F	18.2	19	4.11	6.42	17.8	17.7	L	10.94	1.27	12.57
								R	23.34	3.40	48.51
34.	M	12.5	15	4.00	4.60	13.7	11.2	L	16.03	4.48	55.27
								R	11.29	3.42	29.07
35.	F	17.2	18	4.75	6.00	17.8	15.6	L	24.11	2.14	18.32
								R	26.49	2.23	15.34
36.	M	20.4	22	5.85	7.54	21.7	18.6	L	Coarctated		-
								R			-
37.	M	18.0	19	6.91	8.60	24.5	17.7	L	33.82	13.71	292.0
								R	32.82	9.65	249.0

Table 1. Continuous 2.

Lp.	Hemispheric		Area mm ²	Frontal width mm	Horn length mm	Ventr. triangle		Occip. length mm	Horn		Occipit lobe width mm
	Width mm	Length mm				Width mm	Length mm		Width mm	Area mm	
1.	22.15	73.86	1401.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	No material	No material	21.7	3.66	65.9	17.9
	24.76	74.80	1382.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	No material	No material	20.4	4.90	74.8	17.9
2.	10.35	23.45	204.8	4.18	No material	No material	No material	6.10	5.80	24.2	6.93
	9.77	23.06	215.7	4.41		No material	No material	6.20	5.00	21.9	7.01
3.	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia				
4.	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia				
5.	16.47	39.64	583.0	0.9	1.74	Invisible		12.50	2.73	35.61	10.83
	18.73	40.07	649.9	0.7	2.97	Invisible		13.01	2.97	39.10	10.61
6.	24.20	56.92	1093.0	4.10	14.08	Invisible		20.10	8.67	131.3	18.08
	21.58	54.38	984.0	3.24	17.23	Invisible		18.44	8.10	105.6	20.81
7.	23.89	55.86	1084.0	Demaged material	Demaged material						
	22.80	54.27	912.0								
8.	21.79	55.36	1047.0	1.7	9.67	No material	No material	18.3	6.97	113.5	17.67
	24.09	55.00	1070.0	1.84	9.26	No material	No material	15.1	4.92	52.8	15.17
9.	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia				
10.	18.67	54.21	802.0	2.02	8.86	Invisible		15.3	3.3	21.64	13.7
	20.83	52.42	843.0	Coarctated	Coarctated			13.1	5.22	26.50	16.2
11.	20.14	43.92	719.0	0.5	6.06	Invisible		11.26	3.72	35.41	14.17
	19.00	44.50	676.0	0.7	8.02	4.51	32.4	14.0	2.70	26.59	13.76
12.	16.4	35.34	452.0	6.67	12.02	10.34	144.3	15.52	7.96	106.1	15.19
	17.7	36.15	512.0	5.64	9.63	13.05	182.8	14.49	4.0	53.6	13.58
13.	Deformation	Deformation	Deformation	Deformation	Deformation						
14.	22.96	50.29	570.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	4.80	20.36	13.87	3.22	28.73	16.03
	22.41	52.77	540.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	4.87	28.30	13.32	2.94	31.42	16.00
15.	20.96	46.80	728.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	3.49	34.56	None	5.62	None	14.57
	20.29	49.59	768.0	Coarctated		3.72	21.81	None	5.65	None	15.79
16.	19.07	43.51	649.0	2.59	5.27	8.41	100.9	15.16	4.73	66.81	12.40
	18.40	44.30	649.0	2.88	4.60	8.55	114.2	18.75	4.84	66.76	11.68
17.	25.35	57.38	1116.0	Coarctated		0.86	2.24	14.82	2.78	33.46	16.0
	23.86	57.57	1130.0	Coarctated		3.16	8.45	18.56	4.44	61.01	17.27
18.	21.64	58.16	982.0	0.2	6.69	Invisible		16.89	4.18	42.65	17.10
	22.31	53.06	935.0	0.6	8.18			15.18	3.37	41.45	17.79
19.	18.15	44.35	619.0	0.3	2.82	6.80	26.08	12.10	3.72	40.24	13.09
	18.30	41.85	617.0		Coarctated	7.23	21.65	13.45	2.14	23.43	12.84
20.	6.36	15.27	84.7	3.62	4.45	Unformed		3.40	1.40	4.63	3.50
	6.23	14.22	96.4	3.19	3.90	Unformed		3.10	1.61	3.55	3.47
21.	20.14	44.90	674.0	2.66	6.99	5.51	41.76	16.88	4.32	45.45	16.91
	20.01	46.14	735.0	3.48	6.14	6.91	49.95	18.23	5.21	58.68	16.10

Table 1. Continuous 3.

Lp.	Hemispheric		Area mm ²	Frontal width mm	Horn length mm	Ventr. triangle		Occip. length mm	Horn		Occipit lobe width mm
	Width mm	Length mm				Width mm	Length mm		Width mm	Area mm	
22.	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia	Malacia						
23.	22.56	63.94	1123.0	0.44	5.48	Invisible		13.34	2.17	24.80	17.08
	20.69	64.69	1093.0	0.41	5.98				14.29	3.89	53.95
24.	21.87	48.68	801.0	Coarctated		2.51	5.78	11.03	1.2	14.1	16.45
	20.48	50.55	773.0	Coarctated		3.32	7.20	11.15	1.2	13.0	15.39
25.	22.84	56.10	1010.0	0.4	10.48	5.11	12.06	20.70	4.02	61.01	13.51
	23.04	57.30	1043.0	0.2	10.43	4.72	15.28	20.34	7.16	118.8	19.18
26.	21.42	55.25	911.0	Coarctated		5.25	10.77	4.35	1.07	4.66	12.66
	22.42	55.94	960.0	Coarctated		3.71	10.70	Coarctated	Coarctated	–	13.68
27.	Encaphalocel	Ventricles not formed	Ventricles not formed								
28.	25.79	66.32	1524.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	Invisible		17.46	5.69	79.67	22.94
	25.26	68.56	1458.0						13.79	5.36	58.23
29.	21.24	59.37	1126.0	0.6	5.28	4.50	24.79	18.12	5.35	67.31	17.75
	22.15	57.37	1096.0	Coarctated	Coarctated	5.45	19.03	14.46	5.50	34.04	18.76
30.	18.91	45.84	691.0	1.06	0.93	3.12	7.44	–	0.87	–	15.62
	17.93	46.99	672.0	1.40	1.12	2.20	3.46	–	2.53	–	18.37
31.	19.66	47.99	817.0	Coarctated		6.10	31.98	15.74	3.05	49.57	16.51
	20.21	47.56	811.0			7.40	23.13	16.43	3.57	46.84	17.45
32.	20.45	50.79	856.0	Coarctated		7.09	27.50	17.28	3.95	47.99	15.54
	21.60	51.21	856.0	Coarctated		6.85	30.56	19.36	4.46	54.23	16.78
33.	19.40	47.06	705.0	Coarctated		5.92	19.85	No	No	No	No
	18.77	48.27	744.0			4.99	18.78	13.72	3.26	40.75	19.37
34.	15.45	30.73	378.0	2.89	5.19	9.38	50.40	9.83	2.42	22.25	11.39
	14.87	26.36	323.0	2.66	5.10	7.15	28.40	8.57	1.42	13.39	8.25
35.	16.70	45.41	622.0	2.11	4.66	6.70	24.64	13.06	4.71	49.56	13.49
	20.08	47.07	746.0	1.76	5.40	7.02	25.71	12.19	6.01	59.38	15.46
36.	23.97	51.97	1015.0	Coarctated		6.40	38.81	18.45	4.92	76.79	17.86
	19.46	52.02	953.0	Coarctated		6.11	36.37	14.88	4.29	47.28	16.06
37	40.35	70.30	2143.0	Slit like		14.01	191.0	30.90	20.31	543.0	38.28
	35.61	77.50	2341.0	Slit like		20.50	763.0	33.13	20.29	534.0	34.31

RESULTS

The study was carried out on 37 fetuses from spontaneous abortions, corresponding to weeks 10 to 24 of fetal life. In 5 fetuses, destruction of brain tissue made it impossible to analyze the lateral ventricular system. In 1 case with an advanced CNS anomaly, the ventricular system was not formed.

The assessment of the lateral ventricular system was possible in 31 fetuses (17 male, 14 female).

In the 10th week of pregnancy, balloon-like lateral ventricular bodies and developed horns are observed. The occipital horns are poorly developed. The lateral ventricles are surrounded by a thin layer of nervous tissue, which corresponds with the concept of physiological hydrocephalus (Table 1), (Figure 1).

The frontal horns are initially wide, rounded and much larger than the occipital ones. In the course of further development, the length of the frontal horns increases, and they become very narrow, fissure-like, not exceeding 0.5 mm in width, or their walls are completely adjacent to each other (coarctation). The lateral ventricles

develop according to a similar pattern. As the cerebral hemispheres develop, the ventricular bodies in the axial sections become narrow, fissure-like and wider in the posterior portion. Their shapes in the axial sections are variable, most frequently longitudinal or slightly rounded. The lateral ventricular triangles are located at the junction of the central part (body) with the occipital and temporal horns, and constitute the widest portion of the lateral ventricular system.

In smaller fetuses with signs of physiological hydrocephalus, the lateral ventricular triangles are not developed yet. As the telencephalon grows, the length of the occipital horns increases, and they assume a more stable, cucumber-like shape. They become markedly wider than the frontal and temporal horns. The temporal horns are visible in the axial sections of the brain below the occipital. They have a narrow, fissure-like, C-shaped lumen.

No evident pathology of the cerebral hemispheres was observed in 12 cases, whereas in the remaining 20 (63%) pathological changes were visible: in 10 cases, areas of periventricular leukomalacia; in 5, intra- and periventricular hemorrhages; and in 2 fetuses, ventriculomegaly

Figure 1. Physiological hydrocephalus. Male fetus, 5.41 cm C-R length (10 Hbd).

Abnormal cerebral hemispheres 1									
no	fetuses no.	C-R (cm)	Hbd	Visible pathology	Lateral Ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangle(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
1	1	M	20.0	21	periventricular leukomalacia	right - deformed	no material	coarctation	
2	5	M	15.2	17	malformation in the central and posterior part of the hemispheres	asymmetric	no material	slit like	
3	6	F	19.0	20	intra and periventricular hemorrhage leukomalacia		invisible	asymmetric, wide	width 8 mm
4	8	M	18.0	19	intra-ventricular hemorrhage	asymmetric, deformed	invisible	enlarged	asymmetric
5	10	F	15.5	18	malacia at the vertex of right hemisphere.	asymmetric	invisible	asymmetric	asymmetric

Abnormal cerebral hemispheres 2									
no	fetuses no.	C-R (cm)	Hbd	Visible pathology	Lateral Ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangle(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
6	11	F	17.4	19	leukomalacia in right occipital lobe	slit like	asymmetric	coarctation	asymmetric
7	12	F	12.6	15	Hydrocephalus met US criterion wide aqueduct		L-10 mm R-13 mm	wide	L-8 mm R-4 mm
8	15	M	15.2	19	periventricular leukomalacia		asymmetric	coarctation	
9	16	M	16.2	18	hydrocephalus				
10	18	F	19.8	21	periventricular leukomalacia		invisible	slit like	
11	21	M	18.0	19	intra-ventricular hemorrhage leukomalacia			wide	

Abnormal cerebral hemispheres 3									
no	fetuses no.	C-R (cm)	Hbd	Visible pathology	Lateral Ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangle(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
12	23	F	23.5	24	hemorrhage	hemorrhage	invisible	slit like	
13	24	M	18.7	20	periventricular leukomalacia			coarctation	narrow
14	26	M	19.0	20	periventricular leukomalacia	asymmetry			left narrow right -coarctation
15	27	M	16.0	18	encephalocoele (nullagen chromolias)	complete desorganisation of hemispheres structure			
16	29	M	18.5	20	intra and periventricular hemorrhage			coarctation	
17	30	F	16.0	18	periventricular leukomalacia				

Table 2(1-3). Abnormal cerebral hemispheres.

Figure 2. Ventriculomegaly, binary image. Male fetus, 16.20 cm C-R length. (18 Hbd).

exceeding 10 mm (meeting the USG criteria), including one case with distended aqueduct and markedly increased head circumference in relation to its other dimensions, which indicates active hydrocephalus. In another case, colpocephaly was observed. In one 18-week-old fetus, identical ventricular morphology as in the case of hydrocephalus was noted: generalized lateral ventricular distension with 8.5 mm ventricular triangle width (meeting the criteria of ventriculomegaly according to Farrell and Hertzberg [18]). The remaining 2 fetuses demonstrated developmental anomalies: cranial hernia with cleft palate, ectromelia and eventration in one case, and vascular malformation in the other (Table 2).

After binarization of the axial section images, it is possible to measure the areas of the cerebral hemispheres and the ventricular system (Figure 2).

Asymmetry of the ventricular bodies (central parts), triangles and occipital horns is observed in both normal and pathological brains. In the anomalous brains, asymmetry was more frequent and visible noticeable. Neither noticed distension nor asymmetry of the frontal horns was observed in normal brains, whereas in pathological specimens the frontal horns were often distended and asymmetrical.

The greatest distension was seen in both cases of hydrocephalus: the frontal horns were of semicircular shape, with less marked distension after intra- and periventricular hemorrhages, when they resembled triangles with the base oriented towards the front and frequent significant asymmetry. Among the 5 cases with hemorrhages, the frontal horns were markedly distended and asymmetrical in 3 (60%) (Figure 3).

Only in 1 out of 10 cases of leukomalacia (10 %) did we find asymmetry and distension of the frontal horns. Asymmetry of the triangles was visible both in normal and pathological brains.

The width of the triangles exceeded the ultrasound standard value of 10 mm only in one case of active hydrocephalus (Figure 4) and in one case of colpocephaly. In the second case of ventriculomegaly it reached 8.5 mm, and in the remaining cases it did not exceed 8 mm. The occipital horns were elongated and rounded distally (Figure 4, 5).

Figure 3. Intra- and periventricular hemorrhage. Normal width of lateral ventricular atria. Markedly distended and asymmetrical frontal horns. Female fetus, 19.0 cm C-R length (20 Hbd).

Figure 4. Colpocephaly. Contours of the ventricular system in axial sections. Male fetus, 18.0 cm C-R length (19 Hbd).

Figure 5. Hydrocephalus, giant frontal horns and lateral ventricular atria Female fetus, 12.6 cm C-R length (15 Hbd).

In both normal and pathological brains, the occipital horns were asymmetrical, but the asymmetry was more significant in the pathological specimens (Table 3).

Only in one case of colpocephaly were the occipital horns disproportionately distended to 19 mm in width. In one case of periventricular hemorrhage, the width of the occipital horns exceeded 8 mm.

DISCUSSION

To date, there have been no published data derived from computer-aided analysis of the ventricular system in the prenatal period. The structure of brain tissue is very delicate, which makes it susceptible to deformations even in the case of slight shocks. The technique of computer-aided image analysis makes it possible to perform multiple measurements while avoiding direct manipulation of the preparations and consequent artifacts due to the damage of the nervous tissue. The utility of ELF software in morphological studies was pointed out previously by A. Kędzia et al. [32].

The ELF and Scion for Windows software proved very useful in preliminary processing of the photographic material, elimination of artifacts (e.g. light reflexes), and

enabled us to perform many accurate linear measurements.

The study material comprised brains of fetuses from spontaneous abortions. This explains the high proportion of brains with visible pathologies in the investigated material (63%). Among these, only two cases (with hydrocephalus and colpocephaly) met the USG criteria for ventriculomegaly according to Filly [3] (width of the lateral ventricular atria exceeding 10 mm). Adopting such a standard for 2nd trimester fetuses probably contributes to overlooking numerous pathologies. The standard is characterized by high specificity in the detection of CNS anomalies, but at the same time low sensitivity. In view of the investigated material, the standard values established by Farrell and Hertzberg [18] seem to be more rational: atrial width before the 25th week of gestation should not exceed 8 mm, and before the 17th week, 7.6 mm. In such case, 4 anomalous brains (12%) would meet the criteria for ventriculomegaly.

USG is a standard technique of prenatal evaluation of the CNS. Lateral ventricle images assessed at the level of the atrium are valuable as a screening method in the diagnosis of ventriculomegaly. However, some anomalies may pass undetected in routine USG, especially if the ventricles are not distended, as in the case of agenesis of the corpus callosum [33].

The assessment of the shape of the whole ventricular system is very important. Despite its numerous advantages (low cost, common availability, noninvasive character), USG is associated with some limitations, due to the non-specific appearance of several anomalies, technical factors and ossification of the skull, which interferes with visualization of the brain next to the ultrasound probe and in the posterior cavity at the late stage of gestation. USG often fails to visualize mild parenchyma anomalies [4]. Ultrafast image acquisition techniques in MRI, developed during the recent years, allow more accurate evaluation of the fetal ventricular system in comparison with USG.

In a retrospective analysis of fetal MRI studies, Levine et al. [7] distinguished several patterns of ventricular systems:

- normal;
- slight disproportional distension of the occipital horns with retained general morphology of the ventricular system;

Normal cerebral hemispheres 1									
No	fetus No.	sex	C-R (cm)	Hbd	lateral ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangles(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
1	2	M	6,68	11	Physiological hydrocephalus	uniformed	balloon	wide	
2	7	F	20,2	21			damaged material		
3	14	F	18,2	19	asymmetry		coarctation		
4	17	M	20,5	22	asymmetry	asymmetry	coarctation	asymmetry	
5	19	F	15,5	18	asymmetry				

Normal cerebral hemispheres 2									
No	fetus No.	sex	C-R (cm)	Hbd	lateral ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangles(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
6	20	M	5,41	10	physiological hydrocephalus	uniformed	balloon like	early stage	
7	25	M	20,0	21	asymmetric		slit like	asymmetric	
8	28	F	18,0	19	slit like	invisible	slit like		
9	31	M	18,0	19			coarctation		
10	32	M	19,3	20					

Normal cerebral hemispheres 3									
No	fetus No.	sex	C-R (cm)	Hbd	lateral ventricles plan				
					corpuses	triangles(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
11	35	F	17,2	18			at atrium level		
12	36	M	20,4	22			coarctation	coarctation	

at the level of occipital horns the frontal horns are coarctated

Abnormal cerebral hemispheres 4										
no	fetus no.	sex	C-R (cm)	Hbd	Visible pathology	lateral ventricles plan				
						corpuses	triangles(atrium)	Frontal horns	occipital horns	
18	33	F	18,2	19	extrinsic periventricular leukomalacia				left invisible	
19	34	M	12,5	15	Ventriculomegaly? fetal configuration?			at the triangles level		
20	37	M	18,0	19	macrocephaly, colpocephaly	uniformed				

Table 3(1-4). Normal cerebral hemispheres.

- colpocephaly with or without atypical orientation of the frontal horns;
- atypical orientation of the frontal horns;
- fused frontal horns;
- angular appearance;
- generalized distension of the lateral ventricles;
- malformation of the ventricular system.

Mild disproportion of the occipital horns in relation to the frontal was visible in MRI only. An angular appearance of the lateral ventricles was observed in fetuses with neural tube anomalies. In fetuses with anomalous neural tube and angular pattern of ventricles, the ventricles were markedly smaller (3-12 mm) than in those with neural tube defects and generalized distension (13-25 mm) [7].

In the material we analyzed, the shape of the ventricular bodies was variable, with frequent coarctations (no lumen because of adhesion of the ventricular walls), especially in the anterior portion of the ventricular bodies, as well as asymmetry. The analysis of the frontal horns deserved special attention. At the end of the first trimester, in the 10-12th week of gestation, they are wide and round-shaped, which corresponds to the concept developed by Kłosowski [9] physiological hydrocephalus. In the second trimester, characterized by rapid growth of the cerebral hemispheres, the frontal horns become fissure-like or undergo complete coarctation, visible in transthalamic and transcerebellar sections. In the brains showing no visible pathology, all the frontal horns underwent coarctation or demonstrated a fissure-like appearance, whereas among the anomalous brains, marked distension of the frontal horns reaching down to their ends (visible in transcerebellar sections) was observed in 7 cases (22%) and significant asymmetry in 2 cases. Distension of the frontal horns usually accompanied serious pathologies: hemorrhages in 3 cases, hydrocephalus in 2, a necrotic focus in 1 and vascular malformation in 1. The frontal horns were distended in 3 out of 4 cases, meeting the ultrasonographic criteria of ventriculomegaly according to Farrell and Hertzberg [18].

Coarctation of the frontal horns was observed in most brains with leukomalacia. Evaluation of the frontal

horns seems to be a sensitive method of detecting ventricular anomalies.

Bromley et al. [27] and Patel et al. [28] demonstrated that although 80–90% of fetuses with mild ventriculomegaly are normal at birth, pathological sequelae manifesting at a later time cannot be excluded. According to Gilmore [29], isolated mild ventriculomegaly detected in utero is not associated with complications of pregnancy, but probably due to genetic or environmental factors, which are not commonly regarded as harmful. The accepted upper limit of normal lateral ventricle width has been set at 10 mm [17], although there is a marked diversity of mean atrium width in the published studies. According to Cardoza [15], it is 7.6 mm, according to Pilu [16] 6.9 mm, and according to Farrell et al. [18] 5.4 mm.

The occipital horns are the last to develop, but their primordial forms are visible already in 10-week-old fetuses. Their shape is much more stable than that of the ventricular bodies, and no coarctation is observed in most cases.

CONCLUSIONS

Our observations would tend to indicate that younger fetuses in the second trimester should be assessed according to Farrell and Hertzberg criteria [18], establishing 8 mm as the upper normal limit for the atrium. The results described here are consistent with the analysis of the ventricular system by MRI, concerning the diagnostic significance of the shape of the lateral ventricles, the changes in which depend on the type of central nervous system pathology. In our opinion, the assessment of frontal horns is very useful in the diagnostics of CNS anomalies.

REFERENCES:

- Adams RD, Victor M, Ropper AH: Principles of neurology. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1997
- Harrison MR, Golbus MS, Filly RA: The unborn patient: prenatal diagnosis and treatment. 2nd ed. Philadelphia WB Sanders, 1990
- Filly RA, Cardoza JD, Goldstein RB, Barkovich AJ: Detection of fetal central nervous system anomalies: a practical level of effort for routine sonogram. *Radiology*, 1989; 172: 403-408
- Filly RA, Goldstein RB, Callen PW: Fetal ventricle: importance in routine obstetric sonography. *Radiology*, 1991; 181: 1-7
- Westergaard E: The lateral cerebral ventricles of human foetuses with a crown - rump length of 26-178 mm. *Acta Anat*, 1971; 79: 409-421
- Kubik -Huch RA, Huisman TA, Wisser J: Ultrafast Imaging of the Fetus. *AJR*, 174: 1599-2000
- Levine D, Trop I, Metha TS, Barnes PD: MR imaging appearance of fetal cerebral morphology. *Radiology*, 2002; 223(3): 652-60
- Bartel H: Embryology (in Polish) Warsaw: PZWL, 1995
- Klosowski BN: The development of the brain and its disturbances by harmful factors. Oxford and London: Pergamon Press, 1963
- Drews U: Color Atlas of Embryology. Thieme Stuttgart, 1995
- Carlson BM: Human Embryology and Developmental Biology. Mosby St Louis, 1999
- Shuangshotis S, Netsky MG: Histogenesis of choroid plexus in man. *Am J Anat*, 1966; 118: 283
- Grag BP: Colpocephaly: an error of morphogenesis. *Arch Neurol*, 1982; 39: 242-246
- Nyberg DA: The fetal central nervous system. *Seminars in Roentgenology*, 1990; 25(4): 317-333
- Cardoza JD, Goldstein RB, Filly RA: Exclusion of fetal ventriculomegaly with a single measurement: the width of the lateral ventricular atrium. *Radiology*, 1988; 169: 711-714
- Pilu G, Reece A, Goldstein RB: Sonographic evaluation of the normal development anatomy of the fetal cerebral ventricles. The atria. *Obstetr Gynecol*, 1989; 73: 250-256
- Filly RA, Goldstein RB: The fetal ventricular atrium: Fourth down and 10 mm to go. *Radiology*, 1994; 193: 315-317
- Farrell TA, Hertzberg BS, Kliever MA: Fetal lateral ventricles: Reassessment of normal values for atrial diameter at US. *Radiology*, 1994; 193: 409-411
- Norman MG: Malformations of the Brain, *Journal of Neuropathology and Experimental. Neurology*, 1996; 55: 133-143
- Bannister CM, Russell SA, Rimmer S: Pre-natal ventriculomegaly and hydrocephalus. *Neurol Res*, 2000; 22(1): 37-42
- Yakovlev OL, Wadsworth RC: Schizencephalies: a study of the congenital clefts in the cerebral mantle. II Clefts with hydrocephalus and lips separated. *J Neuropathol Exp Neuro*, 1946; 5: 169-206
- Noorani PA, Bodensteiner JB, Barnes PD: Colpocephaly: frequency and associated findings. *J Child Neurol*, 1988; 3: 100-104
- Goldstein RB, La Pidus AS, Filly RA: Mild lateral cerebral ventricular dilatation in utero: Clinical significance and prognosis. *Radiology*, 1990; 176: 237-242
- Alagappan R, Browning PD, Laorr A: Distal lateral ventricular atrium: re-evaluation of normal range. *Radiology*, 1994; 193: 405: 408
- Greco P, Vimercati A, De Cosmo L: Mild ventriculomegaly as a counselling challenge. *Fetal Diagn Ther*, 2001; 16(6): 398-401
- Gilmore JH, van Tol J, Kliever MA: Mild ventriculomegaly detected in utero with ultrasound: clinical associations and implications for schizophrenia. *Schizophr Res*, 1998; 33(3): 133-40
- Bromley B, Frigoletto FD, Benacerraf BR: Mild fetal lateral cerebral ventriculomegaly: clinical course and outcome. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*, 1991; 164: 863-867
- Patel MD, Filly RA, Hersch D: Isolated mild fetal cerebral ventriculomegaly: clinical, course and outcome. *Radiology*, 1994; 192: 759-764
- Gilmore JH, van Tol JJ, Lewis Streicher H: Outcome in children with mild ventriculomegaly: a case series. *Schizophr Res*, 2001; 48(2-3): 219-26
- Wilhelm C, Keck C, Hess S: Ventriculomegaly diagnosed by prenatal ultrasound and mental development of the children. *Fetal Diagn Ther*, 1998; 13(3): 162-6
- Nicolaides KH, Berry S, Snijders RJM: Fetal lateral ventriculomegaly: associated, malformations and chromosomal defects. *Fetal Diagn Ther*, 1990; 5: 5-14
- Kędzia A, Krakowska H, Błaszczuk E: Evaluation of 'ELF' program usefulness in metrologic examinations of fetal brain. *Folia Morphol*, 1996; 55(4): 318-320
- Bennett GL, Bromley B, Benacerraf BR: Agenesis of corpus callosum: prenatal detection usually is not possible before 22 weeks of gestation. *Radiology*, 1996; 199: 447-450